

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. JOSE RENE A. CEPE

Associate Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

jracepe@yahoo.com

“THE DARK ROAD”

In dark depths, where gossip spreads,
A force of death starts to seep.
Illicit drugs, a seductive disguise,
Kill the soul, pollute the skies.

They provide peace, they provide flight,
But take the heart into the night.
A momentary euphoria, a momentary smile,
But suffering for the soul inside.

The needle beckons, the pill deceives,
With illusions of false happy lives.
What they take, they will steal—
A damaged mind, a compromised seal.

The children are deceived by shallow cheer.
Happy they do not know danger is lurking.
A temporary high, a devil's game,
That fuels addiction, that fuels the flame.

The chain cycle, holding fast,
Take you where you don't want to go.
The world becomes gray, the heart freezes over,
Trapped in a cycle, aging slow.

That promise that was becomes terror.
With each high, a step closer to near.
The illusions are gone, the hopes are dwindling.
The price of drugs, you'll pay.
Every tear real, every loss a wound,
The war is still raging, near and far.
Shattered family, alienated friends
Beneath the burden of a gloomy day.

But there's hope, a path to take,
An opportunity to survive, an opportunity to transcend.
The path to recovery, high and high,
But the path is worth taking; the price is low.

Shout out for help; never too early.
To turn around, to make a change.
You are the power, you are the voice,
To stand up, to be different.

So stand together, solid and strong,
Let love conquer the deceptions they peddle.
For in the battle with the darkness evil,
The ability to change is before your face.

